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Spatial Bayesian modelling applied to the surveys of *Xylella fastidiosa* in Alicante

*M. Cendoya*¹, *J. Martínez-Minaya*², *V. Dalmau*³, *A. Ferrer*³, *D. Conesa*²,
*A. López-Quílez*², *A. Vicent*¹

¹m.cendoya.m@gmail.com, Centre de Protecció Vegetal i Biotecnologia, Institut Valencià d'Investigacions Agràries (IVIA).

²Departament d'Estadística i Investigació Operativa, Universitat de València, Burjassot 46100.

³Servei de Sanitat Vegetal, Conselleria d'Agricultura, Medi Ambient, Canvi Climàtic i Desenvolupament Rural.

The increasing development of techniques applied to species distribution models (SDMs) has allowed them to be widely used in different areas such as ecology and epidemiology. The SDMs are useful tools to establish suitable conditions for the expansion of populations, to evaluate the associations of biotic and abiotic factors with the geographic extent of the species, as well as to predict the species distribution in space and in time. These types of models can be developed through different methodologies. However, many of them ignore the spatial dependence which usually exists among the geographical locations of the observations. This can lead to an overestimation of the parameters and establish false relationships between observations and covariates. Spatial Bayesian hierarchical models allow the inclusion of spatial autocorrelation. Here, this type of modeling was used to analyse the effect of climatic and spatial factors in the distribution of the bacterium *Xylella fastidiosa* subsp. *multiplex* in Alicante (Spain). The presence/absence data of *X. fastidiosa* were obtained from the official surveys gathered in 2017 in the demarcated area of Alicante, where the pathogen was detected affecting almond crops. Climatic covariates were obtained from the WorldClim database. The spatial effect was incorporated through a conditional autoregressive structure (iCAR), while a categorical variable was included based on the “Purcell’s” levels of disease severity based on minimum winter temperature. These thresholds were defined in North America for Pierce’s disease of grapevine, caused by *X. fastidiosa* subsp. *fastidiosa*, and it is unknown if they can be extrapolated to other subspecies or geographic regions. The Integrated Nested Laplace Approximation (INLA) method was used to obtain the posterior distributions of the model parameters. The results show that climatic covariates were not relevant in the model, probably due to the reduced geographic extent of the study area and therefore low climatic variability. However, the pathogen was detected in all “Purcell’s” winter temperature thresholds, confirming the climatic adaptability of *X. fastidiosa* subsp. *multiplex*. In addition, the strong spatial effect observed indicated that the spatial structure has a central role on the dynamics of disease spread.

Keywords: Hierarchical Bayesian models, INLA, *Xylella fastidiosa*.